

ISSN 2181-9599

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9599

ЎТМИШГА НАЗАР

1 МАХСУС СОН

ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ
СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

LOOK TO THE PAST
SPECIAL ISSUE 1

ТОШКЕНТ-2022

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ХОРИЖИЙ ДАВЛАТЛАРДА ГЕНДЕР МАСАЛАСИДАГИ ТЕНДЕНЦИЯЛАР

For citation: Yakhshibeka Abdullaeva, GENDER TENDENCIES IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES. Look to the past. 2022, Special issue 1, pp.16-21

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6758048>

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада хорижий давлатларда гендер масаласида амалга оширилаётган стратегик ҳаракатлар ақс этирилган. Европа давлатлари, Америка, Нидерландия, Африка, Осиё ва бошқа давлатларда раҳбар аёлларнинг давлат бошқарувидаги улуши таҳлил этилган.

Аксарият давлатларда хотин-қизларни қўллаб-қувватлашга бўлган муносабат давлат сиёсатининг устувор йўналишларидан бирига айланганлиги кўрсатилган. Чет эл таълим соҳасидаги аёлларнинг улуши билан Қорақалпоғистон олий таълим тизимидаги хотин-қизларнинг сони таққослаб ўрганилган. Давлат бошқарувида, илм-фанда аёлларнинг роли муҳимлигига эътибор қаратилган.

Калит сўзлар: Таълим, гендер, конституция, ҳокимият, феминизм, хотин-қизлар, ҳуқуқ, Нобель мукофоти.

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ВОПРОСЫ ГЕНДЕРНОЙ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ В ЗАРУБЕЖНЫХ СТРАНАХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье отражены стратегические действия, предпринимаемые по гендерным вопросам в зарубежных странах. Проанализирована доля женщин-лидеров в государственном управлении в странах Европы, Америки, Нидерландов, Африки, Азии и других стран. В большинстве стран отношение к поддержке женщин оказалось одним из приоритетов государственной политики. Количество женщин в системе высшего образования Каракалпакстана сравнивается с долей женщин в зарубежном образовании. Подчеркивается роль женщин в науке и государственном управлении в целом.

Ключевые слова: образование, гендер, конституция, власть, феминизм, женщины, право, Нобелевская премия.

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GENDER TENDENCIES IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES

ABSTRACT

This article reflects the strategic actions taken on gender issues in foreign countries. The share of women leaders in public administration in Europe, America, the Netherlands, Africa, Asia and other countries is analyzed.

In most countries, the attitude towards women's support has become one of the state policy priorities. The number of women in higher education in Karakalpakstan is compared with the share of women in education abroad. The role of women in science and public administration in general is emphasized.

Index Terms: education, gender, constitution, power, feminism, women, law, Nobel Prize.

1. Actuality:

In the current context of globalization, international organizations, research institutes, scientists are engaged in a wide range of issues related to women and gender.

The United Nations Women's Fund (UNIFEM) is a day-to-day foundation that promotes the political and economic role of women in developing countries. UNIFEM mainly works in three areas: increasing the economic opportunities for women to work as entrepreneurs and product producers; assist management and leadership skills in increasing women's participation in decision-making; assisting in providing human rights concerning to women.

UNIFEM is helping to improve the living standards of tens of thousands of women and families in more than 100 countries. It supports programs that are advantageous for women; provides direct technical and financial support to women's initiatives; gives practical lessons, a variety of information to women associations in the implementation of their various programs.

UNIFEM has worked directly with justice officials, police officers and judges to achieve the recognition of women's legal rights in six Central American countries. It is recognized that these activities increase family income and allow women to be more active in their activities [1].

2. Methods and level of study:

In the process of covering the topic, generally accepted historical, comparative analysis, generality and specificity, basic methodological principles of historical thinking, objectivity, systematic methods were used.

3. Research results:

Many years of efforts among states and the international community have shaped new perspectives on the study of gender issues in education. By 2015, one-third of countries in developing regions had achieved gender equality in the primary education system. Most of these countries are located in the Asia and Pacific Ocean regions. In terms of secondary education, the number of female teachers has increased slightly in countries that were previously a minority. Many countries have achieved gender equality in the primary education sector, gradually narrowing the gender gap in secondary and higher education.

The fact that 1975 is called the Year of Women in the World also means that the focus on women has risen to the world level.

In 1985, a conference was held in Nairobi as a report on the 10th anniversary of the International Year of Women. At the same time, a conference of international non-governmental organizations was organized, which was attended by 15,000 representatives of non-governmental organizations. 157 states have adopted the Perspective Strategic Plan until 2000 to further improve the situation of women.

These events led to the birth of the 'idea of global feminism'. It raised the gender aspect to a new level. Attention was paid to all issues related to women.

On December 10, 1948, the UN General Assembly designated December 10 as Human Rights Day.

In 1993, the UN General Assembly adopted the Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Violence against Women [2].

In 1995, the 4th World Conference of Women was held in Beijing. The Beijing Declaration and the Women's Platform were adopted.

On July 2, 2010, the UN General Assembly raised the issue of gender equality and empowerment of women.

In 2014, 143 out of 195 countries in the world guaranteed equality of women with men in their Constitutions. However, 52 states have not yet taken such a positive step.

In 2015, the share of women in the national parliaments of the world was 22% (in 1995 it was 11.3%. - Ya.A.)

Also, November 25 is the International Day for the Elimination of Violence against Women by the United Nations;

February 6 - International Day for the Elimination of Female Genital Surgery;

February 11 - International Women's Day;

June 19 - There is a day marked as "International Day against Sexual Coercion of Women "

In most countries of the world, the number of women involved in public administration is significant. In Sweden, for example, the number of women in parliament increased from 25% to 40% between 1980 and 1984, and by 1995 the number had risen to 50%. The role of women in Finnish socio-political life is constantly growing. Currently, 67 of the 200 seats in parliament are held by women, while the current chairperson and two deputies are women. Since 1994, women have made up 41 percent of government employees. Women make up 30 percent of the Austrian federal government, while in Canada the share of women in the federal service was 42 percent by 1995. The current administration in the United States is the administration with the largest number of women in its history. Women hold more than 2,500 positions (more than 40%). Also, 27 of them are appointed to senior positions by the President.”[3]

Restrictions on women's rights have persisted for various periods in many countries. For example, such restrictions were lifted in 1893 in New Zealand, 1906 in Finland, 1918 in the United Kingdom and Russia, 1944 in France, 1959 in Japan, 1971 in Switzerland, and 1976 in Liechtenstein. This is still the case in some Arab countries (Kuwait, Saudi Arabia).”[4]

Despite the positive changes in the gender landscape in education, much remains to be done in the Asia and Pacific Ocean region. Although girls are allowed to be educated in many countries, they still face many discriminatory barriers to entry into primary and secondary schools, at school, at home, and in society. Similarly, gender barriers, discrimination among teachers, remain a common situation in many places. At the pre-school and primary school levels, the number of female teachers in the humanities and social sciences is predominant, while the number of male teachers in higher education and the natural sciences is predominant. Female teachers face certain barriers in an environment where gender barriers exist from the earliest stages of education to throughout their careers. When teachers are constantly exposed to widespread gender barriers and are unable to take gender aspects into account, it becomes more difficult for them to take a position on gender understanding and leadership in gender issues.

The education system is a mirror that reflects the society as a whole and has an impact on it, and in turn, the ongoing innovations in education also affect the development of society. To succeed in gender equality, the movement must begin with education. Within the education system, teachers have the opportunity to strongly influence the next generation through their activities, behavior, and attitudes toward them. They should be the initiators of change in the introduction of gender equality

In the training of teachers, the process of developing gender aspects and the principles of implementation are the main stages that lead them to the end result. A teacher who understands gender aspects can enable the younger generation to think and act consciously while being aware and

knowledgeable of gender issues. Therefore, the movement for gender equality in education should cover the entire activity of a teacher, from the stage of professional preparation to the stage of continuous professional development.

Between December 2017 and February 2018, UNESCO-Hainan under the joined project “For the Education of Girls and Women” analyzed the situation and the need for professional training of policy makers and teachers for Education sphere in five countries: Cambodia, Myanmar, Nepal, Sri Lanka and Uzbekistan, taking into account gender issues.. Reports from participating countries show that the main factors behind the slow achievement of the goal of gender equality are the lack of awareness and interest of gender stakeholders in education, curriculum designers and textbook developers. Reports suggest that urgent action is needed to develop the capacity of curriculum and textbook developers and those responsible for teacher training. Only then will they be able to better understand gender issues, socio-economic, political and cultural barriers to gender equality in teacher training. An analysis of the fundamental nature of gender inequality in teacher training and professional development is the only and crucial step in addressing the pressing issues of gender inequality.

Women’s role is also great in the development of science. As we know the Nobel Prize was established in 1901 and the first Nobel Prize was awarded to woman in 1903, and that was Maria Skladovskaya Curie. From 1903 to 2020, 892 people and 24 organizations were awarded the Nobel Prize and of these, 58 are women and they make up 6.5 percent. Even 4 women managed to become Nobel laureates 2 times. A total of 77 nationals have won this award. The countries with the most awards are the United States - 383, Great Britain - 132, Russia - 31, Japan - 28, China - 8.

“The Parliamentarians in Support of the Global Movement” has been helping to unite women political leaders around the world. There are 40 women leaders in the world. [5].

In foreign countries, attention is paid to the activities of women in education and science too. However, it should be noted that Canada does not have a clear program for the activities of women in the development of science. Basically, more attention is paid to medicine, genetic engineering and so on.

Below we gave results of analysis on the role of women in the development of education and science at the international level:

According to the 2015 Report of the UNESCO Institute for Statistics, in science – agriculture, technology, medicine, natural sciences, humanities and education – countries with an average share of women above 10%:

Republic of Korea, Japan – 10 percent

In Austria and the Netherlands – 20 percent.

In Switzerland, Sweden, Ireland, Slovakia, Germany, Finland, France, Slovakia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Australia, Norway, Belgium, Canada, USA, Iceland, Greece, Hungary, Chile, the average share of women is over 30 percent.

In Portugal, Israel, Spain, Estonia, Italy, Poland, Turkey, Mexico, New Zealand, the average share of women is over 40 percent.

The average proportion of women is slightly less than fifty to 50 per cent and above, with Luxembourg at 52.8 per cent and Portugal at 49.1 per cent.

In South Africa, the number of women in academic councils and national research organizations is 19 percent, rectors and vice-rectors of higher education institutions 17 percent, university professors 21 percent, and members of the Academy of Sciences 22 percent [6].

The percentage of women in science and technology in Latin America is as follows: Bolivia – 62, Venezuela – 56, Argentina – 53, Paraguay – 52, Uruguay – 49, Brazil – 48, Guatemala – 45 percent.

In the European Union 33% of women contribute to the development of countries, 40% of professors and teachers, 40% of government members and 19% in the private sector.

Among South Asian countries, women make up 8% in Nepal, 14% in India and 32 – 43% in Sri Lanka. Among Southeast Asian countries, Thailand accounts for 52 percent, while the Philippines, Malaysia, Vietnam, Indonesia, Singapore, and Cambodia account for 20 – 30 percent.

In the Arab world, it accounts for 37 percent of the total. Bahrain, Brunei, Sudan account for 40 percent, Jordan, Libya, Oman, Palestine, Qatar for 20 – 25 percent, Saudi Arabia for 1.4 percent, and the United Arab Emirates for 83-84 percent.

In the southern Sahara, female scientists make up 30 percent, in Lesotho and Namibia 60 percent, in South Africa and Zimbabwe 47 percent, and in Burkina Faso 18 percent.

There are special awards for women in Africa. In subsequent years, 5 women have won the Nobel Prize.

The study concluded that one of the most common problems for women when considering objective, subjective reasons is that they are preoccupied with their families, raising their children, and so on. According to some sociological studies, 75% of women enroll to study to become scientists, start their scientific work, but only 35% of them are able to achieve a scientific degree.

For the development of education and science, the European program "HORIZON 2020", planned for 2014-2020, has been developed and funded.

The United States adopted the 1980 Act on Equal Opportunities for Women in Science and Technology.

The share of female students in foreign countries can be seen in the following facts. It is 57% in North America, 49-67% in South America, 40% in Europe and West Asia (excluding Turkey and Switzerland), 30-31% in South Africa, 24% in Asia, 38% in Tajikistan and 39% in Turkmenistan.

In 11 of the 18 Arab states, the number of students is high, at 60-70 percent.

In Europe and North America the average number is 55%, in Italy, Portugal, Romania 26%. 48.5% in Southeast European countries, 44.4% in the Caribbean, 44.3% in Central Asia, 44.3% in Latin America, 40.2% in Western Europe, 36.8% in Arab countries, 34.2% in the European Free Trade Association, The European Union accounted for 33.1 percent, sub-Saharan Africa for 30.0 percent, West Asia for 27.2 percent, Southeast Asia for 29.5 percent and South Asia for 16.9 percent.

The total number of students in higher education institutions of Karakalpakstan is 51,679, of which the number of female students is 27,799, which is 53.8%. There are 4,770 girls studying with a grant, 21,695 under a contract, and 1,334 under a super contract. The number of state awards is 25, the number of orphans and the disabled is 340.

The total number of teachers in 10 higher education institutions in Karakalpakstan is 1,999, of which 966, or 48.3%, are women. There are 251 women with academic degrees and they make up 26.0%. The number of state awards among women is 25 [7].

In the higher education system of Karakalpakstan, the number of women is 48.3% and with a scientific degree 26.0%. So, we are among the countries of Southeast Europe.

There are few rectors (only one) or vice-rectors among women. Deans are 2 people, heads of departments are 30-50% [8]. There are no Nobel Prize winners.

The number of female students in North America (57 percent), South America (49 – 67 percent), European countries (55 percent), and Karakalpakstan was 53.8 percent. From this we can conclude that Karakalpakstan is among the European countries in terms of the number of female students.

4. Conclusion:

Thus, when we study the share of women in the world in education and science, we see that their aspirations for science are great. And, they are making a worthy contribution not only to the science of their countries, but also to the science of the world.

Иқтибослар/Сноски/References:

1. Интернет материаллари: Ziyonet.uz. // Таълим жараёнида раҳбар-аёлларнинг ўқув жараёни самарадорлигини оширишдаги аҳамияти (Internet materials: Ziyonet.uz. // The role of women leaders in the educational process in increasing the effectiveness of the educational process).
2. WWW.un.org.

3. Wollstonecroft M.A. Vindication of the Rights of Women. Harmondsworth, 1985, P. 67. // Қаранг.: Энтони Гидденс. Социология., «Шарқ» нашриёт-матбаа акциядорлик компанияси бош таҳририяти Тошкент – 2002., Б. 203.
4. Wollstonecroft M.A. Vindication of the Rights of Women. Harmondsworth, 1985, P. 67. // Қаранг.: Энтони Гидденс. Социология., «Шарқ» нашриёт-матбаа акциядорлик компанияси бош таҳририяти Тошкент – 2002., Б. 203.
5. WWW.context.reverso.net. Центр женщины-лидеры со всего мира.
6. Доклад ЮНЕСКО по науке на пути к 2030 году. Изд. ЮНЕСКО. Издательский дом Магистр-Пресс. Организация ООН. По образованию, науке, медицине. Россия. Москва. 2016. – С. 95-114. (UNESCO report on science towards 2030. Idz. UNESCO. Publishing House Master-Press. UN organization. Education, science, medicine. Russia. Moscow. 2016. – P. 95-114.)
7. Қорақалпоғистон Республикаси Вазирлар Кенгаши жорий архиви. 2021 йил (Current archive of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. 2021.).
8. Қорақалпоғистон Республикаси Вазирлар Кенгаши жорий архиви. 2021 йил (Current archive of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. 2021.).

ЎТМИШГА НАЗАР

1 МАХСУС СОН

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